
Bedymo User Guide

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Contents:

INTRODUCTION

1.1 What is Bedymo?

The Bergen Dynamical Model (Bedymo) is an idealised atmospheric model developed at the Geophysical Institute of the University of Bergen. The primary target application of Bedymo is to study the mid-latitude storm tracks. But applications are not limited to this region. For example, one of the standard setups available simulates the atmospheric response to localised heating in tropical beta-plane.

The most important unique feature of Bedymo is that it combines a quasi-geostrophic (QG) with a hydrostatic primitive equation (PE) model in one modelling framework, with the aim to make comparisons between QG and PE as consistent and easy as possible. Bedymo solves both QG and PE in terrain-following sigma coordinates. While this choice of vertical coordinate is standard for PE, it is unique for QG. Solving QG in sigma-coordinates provides some additional insight over traditional approaches, because sigma-coordinates exposes the consequences of the QG approximations around the lower boundary more explicitly than traditional approaches with for example a fixed isobar as their lower boundary.

In addition to the two atmospheric dynamical cores, Bedymo contains a slab-ocean model with several different options for wind-induced and prescribed currents, and a passive tracer module which can serve as the basis for the parameterisation of moist diabatic effects. Further, Bedymo comes with (this) relatively comprehensive documentation and a Graphical User Interface (GUI) which allows to control the model and watch the simulation “live” as it evolves. This makes Bedymo easy to setup, and accessible for student projects and teaching.

1.2 When do you want to use Bedymo?

In conclusion, we see two main applications of Bedymo.

As a testbed for atmospheric dynamics Here, Bedymo is a more idealised complement to Held-Suarez-type and aquaplanet simulations. In contrast to these, the Bedymo mid-latitude setups do not contain a Hadley-circulation and consequently no subtropical jets, thus isolating the mid-latitude dynamics from tropical influences.

For student projects and teaching Bedymo can represent many of the idealised representations of the atmosphere as they are discussed in atmosphere/ocean dynamics courses. In particular, Bedymo can represent the shallow water (i.e. barotropic PE), quasi-geostrophic and dry hydrostatic PE systems and allows to easily switch between different approximations.

1.3 Limitations

At the moment, there are a number of limitations with Bedymo. Some important limitations are listed in the following. For most of these, we have plans to resolve, but the respective timelines are unknown and will depend on factors beyond our control.

- No parameterisation of latent heating and moist effects.
- No ocean model that is able to simulate Western Boundary currents.
- No sea-ice.
- No parallel execution.
- No option to use spherical rather than cartesian geometry.
- No option for open boundaries.

1.4 Components of Bedymo

Bedymo follows a very modular approach, designed such that each of the model components can be replaced without technically affecting the other components. Currently, three components are available:

- A combined QG and PE model for the atmosphere.
- A passive tracer module for the atmosphere.
- A slab-ocean model with different options for representing wind-driven currents.

1.5 Scientific documentation and references

The development version of the model code is available at the [UiB GitLAB instance](#). The model code repository also contains the sources of this documentation. Further, the most recent archived and citable versions of the model source code and the user guide can be found here:

- Bedymo source code, doi: [10.5281/zenodo.4715686](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4715686).
- Bedymo User Guide (formally published pdf versions of this document): doi: [10.5281/zenodo.5909782](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5909782) .
- Scientific documentation paper, doi: [10.5194/gmd-2021-84](https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-2021-84).

INSTALLING THE MODEL

2.1 Prerequisites

Bedymo depends on

- A fortran compiler (tested first and foremost with `gfortran`).
- A netCDF library (tested first and foremost with `libnetcdf-4.4.4` with HDF5-support).
- A python environment with `numpy`, `matplotlib`, and `PyQt5` for the graphical user interface.

2.2 Compilation

The model code contains a compile script which defines the compiler and compile options in the uppermost section (called section 0). Possible settings are comprehensively documented there. When compiling on a not yet defined host system, you will likely need to adapt section 1a of the compile script to your specific setup. Use the existing configuration for host systems at the University of Bergen and MacOS (with homebrew) will as reference for your new host configuration.

RUNNING THE MODEL

If the compilation was successful, you will have all necessary files to run Bedymo in the `run`-folder of the Bedymo source root directory. In particular, you will find there:

- The main executable `bedymo.x`. Use this executable to run Bedymo without GUI.
- An example configuration file `bedymo_std.nml` showcasing one of the predefined standard setups.
- A python module `bedymo*.so`. This python module makes the core controls as well as the model variables available as a python module. This python module also provides the basis for the GUI.
- A python runsript `runscript.py`, showing how to run the model (without GUI) and access model variables through python.
- A python runsript `bedymo_gui.py` which provides model controls through a GUI.

In this folder you can run the model by simply executing either the main executable `./bedymo.x`. It will the start running the example setup in the configuration file. For each run, Bedymo will write both a status log and a report, called `bedymo_status.XXXX.log` and `bedymo_report.XXXX.log`, where `XXXX` is an increasing counter of model simulations.

The status log contains a line for each time step in the execution, containing the time step count, time step in seconds, and lead time in seconds followed by a number of internal diagnostics that can help debug the model.

The report file provides brief summary of the model simulation, with start and end dates, name of the host on which the model was run, compile-time information, and a copy of the model configuration. The report files are designed such that they are valid model configuration files, so they can be used to rerun the model with the same configuration.

Finally, if so specified in the model configuration, Bedymo will produce a `bedymo_result.nc` output file. Note that the result file is NOT protected against accidental overwrites as the report and status files, its file name does not include the `XXXX` counter. So if you run the model several times in the same folder and need to keep the output, you will need to manually rename/move the output file. This is to avoid the model filling up (even large) disk areas by accident.

3.1 Running with BedymoGUI

Alternatively, in order to start the GUI, you only need to execute the provided script via `python bedymo_gui.py`. Currently, the namelist and initialisation used for BedymoGUI is hardcoded in the script to be the default file names `bedymo_std.nml` and `bedymo_init.nc`. If you need to change these file names, you can do so in the script, just look for the line containing the call to the `init_bedymo()` function and adapt as required.

The GUI contains both a large plot area displaying the selected model field, as well as a number of control panels, see screenshot below. These control panels allow to:

- Control which variable and level is shown in the plot area.
- Control the model (start & stop integration, single-step).
- Display some most relevant sections of the model configuration.

The model controls also allow to extend the model run beyond the configured number of time steps/lead time in the model configuration `bedymo_std.nml`. Access to all other configuration variables is read-only.

3.2 Using a predefined standard setup

Bedymo comes with a set of standard setups to illustrate its capabilities. They are also well-suited to be the basis for your own model setups. The available setups are in the `run_config` folder. They are

- `bedymo_std.nml.pe_cyclogenesis`: An initial baroclinic zone balanced by a jet in a zonally periodic mid-latitude channel. A small initial perturbation triggers the development of a primary and secondary cyclone. The integration stops after 10 days.
- `bedymo_std.nml.pe_channel`: As above, but including temperature relaxation to replenish the baroclinicity used by the growing cyclones. With the relaxation, the model arrives at a state that is roughly statistically stationary after about 300-500 days. The integration stops after 1000 days.
- `bedymo_std.nml.pe_mountain`: A mid-latitude channel without initial baroclinicity but a surface pressure gradient balanced by homogeneous geostrophic winds. The model domain contains an isolated Gaussian mountain which triggers a stationary planetary wave in its lee.

- `bedymo_std.nml.pe_igwmount`: A smaller-scale mid-latitude channel on an f-plane and without initial baroclinicity but a surface pressure gradient balanced by homogeneous geostrophic winds. The model domain contains an isolated Gaussian mountain which triggers a stationary inertia-gravity wave in its lee.
- `bedymo_std.nml.pe_coupled_matsuno_gill`: A coupled setup using the slab ocean with equatorial beta-plane. The atmosphere is initialised by balanced homogeneous easterlies, the slab ocean with an isolated Gaussian SST anomaly which triggers a Matsuno-Gill type response in the tropical atmosphere. In this default setup, the atmospheric flow does not induce currents in the ocean.

Most of the setups also have a QG variant with `qg` instead of `pe` in the file name.

A detailed description of each standard setup is in [Available standard setups](#).

3.3 Switching between QG and PE

To switch between QG and PE for any setup, three configuration items need to be adapted:

- `dt` in the `numerics` namelist. As there are no inertia gravity waves in QG, we can use a much longer time step to speed up the simulation. For 100 km horizontal resolution, the standard setups use time steps of 180 seconds for PE and 1200 seconds for QG.
- `ladv_prog` and `ladv_vert` in the `physics` namelist. Only for PE, horizontal advection is by the prognosed horizontal wind components (`ladv_prog = T`) and vertical advection is enabled (`ladv_vert = T`).

3.4 Full model configuration

Once you are comfortable to run the predefined model setups, feel free to adapt the configuration to your needs. The model can be configured through a configuration file, typically called `bedymo_std.nml`. This file contains several Fortran namelists, each containing configuration variables as key-value pairs. The following tables describe the namelists one by one.

3.4.1 Shared configuration for all model components

The `models` namelist

Which of the available model components are to be used for the simulation?

Configuration key	Type	Description
<code>latmos_bedymo</code>	logical	Use the combined QG/PE atmospheric model?
<code>latmos_bedmope</code>	logical	Use the optimised PE atmospheric model (currently defunct)?
<code>latmos_add_trace</code>	logical	Use the atmospheric tracer module?
<code>locean_slab</code>	logical	Use the slab-ocean module?

The numerics namelist

The name list defines parameters used in the time integration and advection.

Configuration key	Type	Description
nt	integer	Number of time levels for prognostic variables.
dt	integer	Model time step in seconds.
alpha	real	Coefficient of the Robert-Asselin-Williams filter for leap frog.
adv_order_max	integer	Numerical order used for the discretisation of the advection.
int_scheme_id	integer	ID for the time integration scheme.

The timectrl namelist

The name list defines parameters that control time-related aspects, in particular the length of the simulation and the output interval.

Configuration key	Type	Description
lout	logical	Save simulation results (i.e. write a netCDF file)?
loutinit	logical	Save initialisation?
loutend	logical	Save end of model run?
tstop	integer	If above zero, number of time steps to run.
tsstop	integer	If above zero, length of simulation in seconds.
dtout	integer	Interval between two outputs, in seconds.

The grid namelist

The name list defines the common grid used for all models and the initialisation program.

Configuration key	Type	Description
nx	integer	Number of grid points in x-direction.
ny	integer	Number of grid points in y-direction.
nz	integer	Number of grid points in z-direction.
dx	real	Grid distance in x-direction in meters.
dy	real	Grid distance in y-direction in meters.
ztop	real	The altitude of the model top in meters.
lcoriolis	logical	Enable Coriolis force?
lbetaeffect	logical	Enable beta-Effect for Coriolis force?
fcor	real	Primary Coriolis parameter f_0 .
betacor	real	Secondary Coriolis parameter β .
latbdrtyp_ew	integer	Boundary type ID for eastern and western boundaries.
latbdrtyp_sn	integer	Boundary type ID for southern and northern boundaries.

The topo namelist

The name list defines the common topography used for all models and the initialisation program.

Configuration key	Type	Description
top_surftyp	integer	If above zero, surface type ID for the topography.
top_amp	real	Amplitude parameter for the topography surface.
top_lx	real	If above zero, length scale in x-direction for the topography surface.
top_ly	real	If above zero, length scale in y-direction for the topography surface.
top_cx	integer	If above zero, center point index in x-direction for the topography surface.
top_cy	integer	If above zero, center point index in y-direction for the topography surface.

The metio namelist

The name list defines output parameters used for all models and the initialisation program. This name list will only take effect if `lout` is set in the `timectrl` name list.

Configuration key	Type	Description
loutbdr	logical	Save additional helper boundary points outside the model domain?
lcoards_compatible	logical	Make sure the results netCDF file adheres to the COARDS standard?

3.4.2 Configuration specific to a model component

The following namelists are specific one of the model components. If the corresponding component is not activated in the `models`-namelist described above, the corresponding namelists will be ignored.

The physics namelist

This namelist configures the combined QG/PE-model which can be activated with `latmos_bedymo=T`.

Configuration key	Type	Description
init_type	integer	Initialisation ID for one of the standard model setups.
lbasic	logical	Add a basic-state flow to the model setup, as for example from the confluence-shear model used to study frontogenesis in an idealised framework.
basic_type	integer	Basic state flow ID.
lforce	logical	Apply diabatic or prescribed forcing to the temperature tendency?
ladv	logical	Enable advection (applies to all variables)?
ladv_const	logical	Keep advection constant at its initial value?
ladv_ageo	logical	Enable ageostrophic advection (for SG)?
ladv_prog	logical	Enable prognostic advection (for PE)?
ladv_vert	logical	Enable vertical advection (for PE)?
lthermal_pres	logical	Enable thermal influence of pressure/geopotential fields?
lanelastic	logical	Disregard horizontal variations in density in the PE model?
lsurf_friction	logical	Enable linear friction in the lowest model level(s)?
ldamp	logical	Enable ∇^2 -damping?
vert_profile_type	integer	Initial stratification profile ID.
ekman_coeff	real	Linear friction parameter.
damp_coeff	real	Damping parameter.
relax_coeff	real	Relaxation coefficient for temperature relaxation.
swamp_depth	real	<i>Currently unused.</i>

The tracer namelist

The name list configures the optional tracer component, which can be added to one of the atmospheric models and activated by setting `latmos_add_trace=T` in the models name list.

Configuration key	Type	Description
lhumidity	logical	Add three tracer variables with suggestive names for a future convection parameterisation.
lpassive	logical	Enable passive tracers additional to the humidity-related ones?
npas	integer	Number of passive tracers to add.

The slabocean namelist

The name list configures the optional slab ocean component, which can be added to one of the atmospheric models.

This name list will only take effect if `locean_slab` is set in the `models` name list.

Configuration key	Type	Description
<code>lcurrent_ekman</code>	logical	Enable ocean advection by Ekman currents?
<code>lcurrent_prescribed</code>	logical	Enable ocean advection by prescribed currents?
<code>lreservoir_prescribed</code>	logical	Enable upwelling with rescribed reservoir temperature?
<code>lrelaxation</code>	logical	Enable ocean temperature relaxation?
<code>relaxation_coeff</code>	real	Ocean temperature relaxation coefficient.
<code>drag_coeff</code>	real	Ocean-atmosphere momentum exchange coefficient.
<code>sh_exchange_coeff</code>	real	Ocean-atmosphere heat exchange coefficient.
<code>mixed_layer_depth</code>	real	Depth of the slab ocean layer.

AVAILABLE STANDARD SETUPS

All standard setups are described in the section on *Scientific documentation and references*. The scientific documentation paper for BedyMo contains illustrations and discussion of different variants of these standard setups. For this reason, we here limit the documentation to a brief introduction followed by a summary of some key aspects of the model configuration for each standard setup.

4.1 Cyclogenesis in a baroclinic channel

This setup is focused on the development of a primary cyclone from an initially small perturbation. The most rapid deepening of the cyclone happens after about 84 hours of lead time after which the primary cyclone has reached its mature stage. Downstream of the primary cyclone a series of secondary cyclone developments, the first of which reaching its mature stage around 120 hours of lead time. Eddy kinetic energy in QG cyclones tend to develop a little more rapidly than PE cyclones. PE cyclones tend to be smaller, deeper and associated with steeper surface pressure gradients.

Key aspects of the configuration

- Mid-latitude channel with periodic boundaries in x-direction, walls in y-direction: `latbdrtyp_ew = -1` and `latbdrtyp_sn = 0`.
- Beta-plane with Coriolis parameters corresponding to 50N: `fcor = 1.117e-4` and `betacor = 1.472e-11`.
- Initialisation of a baroclinic zone with temperature perturbation `init_type = 0`.
- Neither friction nor damping: `lsurf_friction = F` and `ldamp = F`.
- The model is run up to a lead time of 10 days with output saved every 6 hours: `tsstop = 864000` and `dtout = 21600`.
- Horizontal resolution of 100 km, 3 levels in the vertical: `dx = 100000.`, `dy = 100000.`, and `nz = 3`.

4.2 Storm track in a baroclinic channel

This storm track setup is closely linked to the above cyclogenesis setup, but focusses on the mean storm track statistics rather than the initial development. Baroclinicity is restored through temperature relaxation and winds experience linear surface friction as well as scale-selective damping of the predominantly the smallest scales. After about 500 days of lead time the model achieves a statistically stationary state in which there no longer is a discernible trend in the sea-level pressure distribution within the model domain. We therefore recommend focussing on lead times larger than 500 days for analyses of the storm track properties.

Key aspects of the configuration

Domain setup and initialisation as above, but including

- Surface friction and damping: `lsurf_friction = T` and `ldamp = T`.
- Temperature relaxation back towards the initial values: `relax_coeff = 1.0e-6`.
- The model is run much longer with `tsstop = 86400000`, corresponding to 1000 days.

4.3 Planetary waves excited by isolated orography

An isolated idealised mountain triggers planetary waves in a mid-latitude beta-plane. The emerging stationary wave in the lee of the mountain closely follows the prediction from linear stationary wave theory. In order to keep the solution close-to-linear, the mountain is only about 10 meters high. This is just enough to elicit a response that is larger than inertia-gravity waves caused by small initial imbalances in PE.

Key aspects of the configuration

- Again a mid-latitude channel with periodic boundaries in x-direction, walls in y-direction: `latbdrtyp_ew = -1` and `latbdrtyp_sn = 0`.
- Initialisation with horizontally homogeneous temperatures and homogeneous westerlies: `init_type = 2`.
- Beta-plane with Coriolis parameters corresponding to 50N: `fcor = 1.117e-4` and `betacor = 1.472e-11`.
- An isolated Gaussian mountain with $100 \text{ m}^2/\text{s}^2$ height and meridional/zonal scales of 15 and 10 grid points, respectively: `top_surftyp = 2`, `top_amp = 100.`, `top_ly = 15.`, and `top_lx = 10.`
- Comparatively large vertical resolution to better resolve vertical wave propagation: `nz = 10`.

4.4 Inertia-gravity waves excited by isolated orography (PE-only)

An isolated idealised mountain triggers inertia-gravity waves in a mid-latitude f-plane. The mountain is considerably smaller in horizontal extent than in the above planetary wave setup, and the model resolution is correspondingly higher. The emerging stationary wave pattern in the lee of the mountain closely follows the prediction from linear stationary wave theory. The QG system cannot represent inertia-gravity waves, such that this standard setup is available for PE only. As with the planetary wave setup, the mountain is just high enough to elicit a response that is larger than inertia-gravity waves caused by initial imbalances.

Key aspects of the configuration

- Again a mid-latitude channel with periodic boundaries in x-direction, walls in y-direction: `latbdrtyp_ew = -1` and `latbdrtyp_sn = 0`.
- Initialisation with horizontally homogeneous temperatures and homogeneous westerlies: `init_type = 2`.
- f-plane to remove potential impact from Rossby waves, with Coriolis parameters corresponding to 50N: `fcor = 1.117e-4` and `betacor = 0`.
- An isolated Gaussian mountain with $100 \text{ m}^2/\text{s}^2$ height and meridional/zonal scales of 7.5 and 5 grid points, respectively: `top_surftyp = 2`, `top_amp = 100.`, `top_ly = 7.5`, and `top_lx = 5.`
- Large horizontal resolution of 10 km, 30 levels in the vertical to properly resolve vertical wave propagation: `dx = 10000.`, `dy = 10000.`, and `nz = 30`.

4.5 Surface heating in an equatorial beta-plane (PE-only, coupled)

An isolated tropical SST anomaly centred on the equator heats the atmosphere in an equatorial beta-plane, and excites both a Rossby wave and an equatorial Kelvin-wave. The wave responses follow the expectations from the linear theories of Matsuno and Gill. The solution changes considerably once the atmosphere is set to induce Ekman transport in the ocean mixed layer (`lcurrent_ekman = T`). Further, the solution changes character fundamentally once the divergent wind-induced Ekman transport over the equator is set to upwell colder waters into the mixed layer (`lreservoir_prescribed = T`). The model domain contains the equator, such that this setup is only available for the PE model.

Key aspects of the configuration

- The setup includes the slab-ocean `locean_slab = T` with a mixed-layer depth of 50 m: `mixed_layer_depth = 50`.
- An equatorial channel with periodic boundaries in x-direction, walls in y-direction: `latbdrtyp_ew = -1` and `latbdrtyp_sn = 0`.
- Equatorial beta-plane: `fcor = 0`. and `betacor = 1.472e-11`.
- Initialisation with horizontally homogeneous temperatures and homogeneous easterlies: `init_type = 3`.
- By default, no wind-induced currents in the slab-ocean: `lcurrent_ekman = F`.

EXTENDING THE MODEL

5.1 Overall organisation of the model code

The model source code is structured to be as modular as possible. This means for example that generic model infrastructure such as the numerical schemes, grid definitions and input/output-routines are as detached from the actual physical formulation of the model as reasonably possible within the limitations of Fortran. Further, the different physical models are all self-contained and can be run independently from each other; add-ons to physical models such as the atmospheric tracer module are formulated such that they will work without adaptation with each of the available atmospheric models.

Some specific consequences of this modular approach are:

- Model components need to register themselves which variables are to be included in the netCDF output.
- Model components need to register the variables required for the exchange with other model components.
- Fortran modules need to define their own routines for initialisation and termination, called `init_<module_name>` and `term_<module_name>` as far as relevant.
- All relevant API to run the model is contained in the `runctrl` module. This module coordinates the overall initialisation and termination of a model simulation. The `runctrl` module is used in both the Fortran executable and the python runscripts.
- Preprocessors share the model numerics and grid definitions and all other generic infrastructure in `src_base` and `src_numerics`.
- Different model components can be switched on/off both at compile time and (as far as available in the executable) for each model simulation. Each model component thus needs to be guarded by a compile-time switch to include/exclude the model from the compilation.

The following table gives a brief overview over the functions and content of each Fortran module in an order in which all interdependencies between modules have been resolved (i.e. modules depend on only on other modules that appear earlier in the list). The first list of modules contains the basic infrastructure and numerics used for all physical models and the preprocessors.

Fortran module	Folder	Description
kind	src_base	Defines the numerical precision used throughout.
ptr	src_base	Fortran boilerplate necessary to define and use procedure pointers.
consts	src_base	Defines physical constants and model parameters.
logfile	src_base	Defines the report and status files and functions for error reporting.
surflib	src_base	Defines parameterised 2d-functions, e.g. Gaussian ridges and hills.
ncin	src_base	Reads netCDF files for initialisation/restart.
config_base	src_base	Defines and parses the grid, topo and metio namelists.
grid	src_base	Defines various grids (main, staggered, multigrid for the QG-inversion).
interpolate	src_numerics	Defines interpolation functions between grids of different resolutions.
boundaries	src_numerics	Defines different boundary conditions and makes them available in a common interface.
ellipse	src_numerics	Defines routines to solve elliptical PDEs, for example to do a Laplace-inversion.
derivatives	src_numerics	Defines derivatives on the grid at different numerical precision.
timeint	src_numerics	Defines abstract time integration routines.
coupler	src_base	Defines the interfaces used to exchange information between model components.
ncout	src_base	Writes results from the simulation as netCDF output.

With all these basics established, we can proceed to define the different physical model components. The model components each typically contain several Fortran modules. Typically each model component contains

- a configuration module defining the model-specific namelists,
- a module containing functions to calculate diagnostic variables, and
- a module containing the prognostic equations and a function advancing the model by a time step.

Currently, the following physical models are available:

Model component	Folder	Description
bedymo	src_atmos	Physical core of the namegiving QG/PE model.
bedymoPE	src_atmos	An optimised PE model (currently defunct).
trace	src_atmos	An atmospheric passive tracer module.
slab	src_ocean	A slab-ocean with different parameterisation for prescribed and wind-induced currents.

With all physical models defined, the `src_core` folder contains first and foremost the `runctrl` module which orchestrates all of the above and provides functions to initialise, run and terminate the model. These functions are used in the Bedymo standalone executable defined in `bedymo_main` and the python runscripts.

Fortran module	Folder	Description
config_run	src_core	Defines and parses the models, numerics and timectrl namelists.
runctrl	src_core	Provides the API to run the model for the Fortran executable and the python runscripts.
bedymo_main	src_core	Defines the Fortran executable and its command line options.

Finally, preprocessors are defined in the `src_pre` folder. Currently there is only one preprocessor available which can be used to define custom idealised initial conditions for Bedymo.

Preprocessor	Folder	Description
<code>init</code>	<code>src_pre</code>	Defines an executable to create custom idealised initial conditions for Bedymo.

5.2 Adding parameterisations and model components

Given the modular approach and the comprehensive basic infrastructure it is relatively straightforward to add new model components to Bedymo. The existing physical models provide a template on how to best structure the new code to fit into the modelling framework.

The only place where existing code must be touched to include a new model component is the `runctrl` module. Here, the new model component must be included in the model initialisation and termination choreography as well as in the function that advances all model components by a time step. With that in place, remember to document the new model component

1. in the top section of the `compile` script, listing the models that can be included in the compilation.
2. this documentation page defined in the `doc/source-directory` of the model code repository.

Note that parameterisations beyond a certain complexity are best included as new model components similar to the tracer module. This allows to enable/disable/configure the parameterisations independently from, for example, the atmospheric model which they hook onto.

Happy coding!

INDICES AND TABLES

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